

Text, Theatrical Processions and Space : Bakasura-vadha, Arjuna-tapassu, and Uttra-gograhanam in Dharmaraja's festival

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Abstract :

One of the significant features of the Dharmaraja's festival is organizing theatrical performances at various places such as village streets, temple sites and farm fields. Few of the theatrical performances are organized with theatrical processions at outdoor sites, and they are Bakasura-vadha, Arjuna-tapassu and Uttara-gograhanamu. The aim of this paper is to study text, processions, and space in these performances. Literature, observation and participatory methods are used to study these performances. The literature survey reveals that these performances are not studied in the context of processional enactments. This study finds performance space of the processional enactments and its relation to the text in the festival. There are five outdoor theatre performances in Dharmaraja's festival, and few of them are accommodated with processional enactments. Because of this reason, three performances are selected for this research. This study witnesses the importance of text, processional enactments and space in the selected performances.

Keywords : Text; space; processions; outdoor theatre; and Dharmaraja's festival.

Introduction :

In Southern India, specifically in Tamil speaking region, many temples are dedicated to Dharmaraja, the eldest brother of five Pandavas. Dharmaraja's temples are usually called as Draupadi's temples with reference to common wife of the five Pandava brothers. At

these temples, "VannikulaKshyatriyas"¹ play significant role in worshipping Pandavas; yearly once, they organize a festival with rituals, theatre and processions. This annual festival is celebrated in spring or summer, and lasts about 18 to 30 days. The festival is totally rooted in history and culture of Vannikula Kshatriyas. However, other communities also worship Pandavas, and collaborate to celebrate the festival.

During the festival, rituals, theatre and processions are performed at several places: temple courtyards, farm fields, and shrines. The theatre performances include with Harikatha and "VeedhiNatakamu". Many processions are organized with short and long intervals at the festivals. These processions are observed at temple rituals and theatre performances during the festivals. Some of the processions are associated purely with theatre performances at outdoors. These theatre performances are killing of Bakasura-vadha, Arjuna-tapassu, and Uttara-gograhanam. An outdoor theatre performance is both precedes and follows by the theatrical processions in the festival. Usually, the theatrical processions are performed in village streets, temple sites or farm fields. The theatrical processions establish a strong connection with the text and performance. It is also very important to understand both processional and theatrical spaces of these performances. Thus, this paper studies space, theatrical enactments, and space in these performances.

Literature Review:

The literature review show that Dharmaraja's festival studied in the context of the rituals and theatre. For instances, Alf Hildebeitel studied Dharmaraja's festival in the context of rituals, and Richard Frasca and Hanne Bruinne investigated theatre performances in the festival. These scholars' work also has thrown light in Dharmaraja's festival in Telugu region. Apart from these scholars, many scholars focus on Dharmaraja's festivals and its theatre performances in Telugu region. These scholars and their works are Bhakthavatsal Reddy, Draupaid Tirunallu (Dharmaraaju Tirunallu); Govinda Reddy, Chittoor Jilla Veedhi Natakalu-Oka Pariseelana; Vasudeva Singh, Kangundi Kuppam Veedhi Natakalu; Paidala Moulana, Chittoor Jilla Tiruanall Geyalu; Genji Aruna, Chittoor Zilla Pandugalu; Medukondu Shankar, Kuppam Veedhi Natakamu-A Performance Study; Pejjai Nagaraju, Draupadi Thirunallu A study of scenographic elements in the performances. Previous studies have almost exclusively focused on either rituals or theatre. There has been less previous evidence for processional enactments and its text in Dharmaraja festival.

Research Methods :

This study uses both literary and ethnography research methods. Literary survey used to understand the rituals, text and the festival process; ethnography is adapted to understand the performance space, processions, and integration of the text. From ethnography method, participatory observation and interview methods are used to collect the data related rituals, processions, and enactments in

Dharmaraja's festivals in the area of Chittoore district, Andhra Pradesh.

1. Basura-vadha (Killing of Bakasura) and processional enactment of Bhima fighting:

The performance of Bakasura-vadha in Dharmaraja's festival explains how Bhima collects the food in village, and how he fights with Bakasura. Bakasura-vadha is also known as Bandi-kumbham. The performance dominates with processional enactments. The performance space of Bakasura-vadha is extended from temple courtyards to village corners.

1.1. Summary of Bakasur-vadha :

Bakasura, a demon in the Mahabharatha, uses to command village Ekachakra. At the same time, in the village, Pandavas live in the disguise of Brahmins. They use to beg for food, and bring it to home. Kunti, Pandava's mother, divide it, and offers large amount of it to Bhima. One day, she hears a woman's cry from the neighbor's house. Kunti enquires the reason behind her weeping. Kunti comes to know that people of Ekachakra have made an arrangement with Bakasura, a giant. According to the arrangement, each family of village has to send person from their family as a good to Bakasura. Kunti consoles the poor woman and promises to send Bhima in the place of the woman's son. Next morning, Bhima drives a bullock cart with food to the Bakasura. As he cannot resist his hunger, Bhima eats all the food intended for Bakasura. When he comes to know that, Bakasura is very much annoyed. Then, Bakasura and Bhima fights, and Bakasura is killed by Bhima. From this story, the events of Bhima driving bullock cart and the fight between Bhima and Bakasura are performed with processional enactment in the festival.

1.2. Performance of Bakasura-vadha :

Bakasura-vadha is first outdoor theatrical performance in the festival and it is locally popular with the names of Bakasura-vadha and Bandi-khumbhamu. Performance space of Bakasura-vadha is an extension of theatrical space in to streets of villages which organizes the festival. Bakasura-vadha is combination of processional enactment and a short Veedhi-Natakamu performance in outdoors. It is performed by two Veedhi-Natakamu Performers: one to play role of Bakasura, and other one to play role of Bhima. Bakasura-vadha begins and ends with rites; in between the rites, there is a processional enactment that is performed from the corners of the village to the temple yards.

Bullock cart is the center of the theatrical procession, and it visually dominates in the large-scale setting. On the day of the performance, a bullock cart is decorated with “leaves of banana, neem, and coconut; flowers; and powder of vermilion and turmeric”. Along with the bullock cart, two bulls are part of the performance. These bulls’ horns and forehead are decorated with turmeric and vermilion paste. Usually, the performance begins between 2pm to 4pm. By the time the performance begins, the decorated bullock cart is occupied with idols of Bhima and a Brahmin. In front of the cart, two actors are prepared with costumes and makeup to play the characters of Bakasura and Bhima. Then, the officiants of the temple perform rituals of Harathi and break the coconut in front of the cart to commence the theatrical procession.

1.3. Theatrical processions to collect the food :

The processional enactment begins at the temple, reaches various corners of the village, and reaches back to the temple yards. The entire procession is accompanied by three group of music bands: *melam*, *pamba*, and *dappu*. The procession can be categories into four group: music bands, actors, bullock cart, and devotees. The music bands lead the procession, two actors in the characters follow the musical band, and the cart follows the actors. The devotees surround these three groups and follow them to witness the procession. Here, the movement of the devotees is similar to the mass march. This procession reaches every house in the village.

When it approaches a house in the village, the procession is halted for two minutes to perform a rite. Here, to complete the rite, the people from the house offers turmeric water to the cart by throwing it under the cart and burning camphor. After the rites, they offer boiled rice, vegetable curry, *kudumulu*⁷, and sweets. Once the food is collected from a house and stored in the vessels kept in the cart, then the procession reaches to another house. Thus, the offered food is collected from various houses in the village.

At the junction of the streets, the performers create fighting poses and demonstrate vigorous moves. Part of the processional enactment, both the actors perform acrobatic moves to convey that Bakasura and Bhima fighting. It is observed that Bakasura character is represented with “cavorts about the cart demonically, leaping, jumping, and screaming” (Hiltebeitel, 1: 171).

The two character, in most of the procession, chase, warn, and argue each other. In few cases, both the characters push each other, and devotees separate them. In this way the processional enactment is performed in the streets by the two actors.

After collecting food from the villagers, the procession returns to the temple premises. Then, the collected food is shifted from the cart to a huge white cloth which is spread out on the ground in the temple courtyard. Here, both the characters sit other sides of the food on the cloth. Now, Bhima initiates to eat the food which is intended for Bakasura. Watching Bhima, Bakasura is furious and starts to fight with Bhima. Thus, the battle between Bhima and Bakasura begins with comic actions, acrobatic moves, and jumps. Finally, the performers demonstrate the killing of Bakasura with symbolic action.

1.4. Extended Performance Space in the Village :

The village streets temporarily represent sacredness during the processional enactment. The space is spread around the village streets and temple courtyards for the performance of Bakasura-vadha. This space is enriched with rangoli and folk decorations. In case of processional enactments, the temple committee determines the processional routes. These processional routes are decorated with rangoli art by the entire village community. At the temple yards, the space is already decorated by the temple committee with the help of folk decorators. The processional pathway is just simply a street, and it is transformed into a sacred path by the presence of the performers,

the bullock cart, and the Bhima icon. The sacred path reverts to its previous state once the procession has passed from there. Thus, the procession path vibrates with sacred visuals for a short moment during the processional enactment of Bakasura-vadha.

2. Arjuna-tapassu (Arjuna's penance) :

Arjuna-tapassu is about Arjuna performing penance on Indrakeeladri. It is also known as Tapas-manu in Dharamaraja festival. Arjuna-tapassu describes how Arjuna obtains the "deadly weapon Pasupatha", and it is also one of the "large-scale enactments" performed in the temple courtyards. This performance begins with a procession around the temple. The main story is performed at a large pole with rituals and folk theatrical elements.

2.1. Summary of Arjuna-tapassu :

Background story of Arjuna-tapassu starts when Vyasa advises Pandavas to acquire "deadly weapon Pasupatha". Listening to Vyasa's advice Dharmaraju instructs Arjuna to obtain the deadly weapon. Then, Arjuna intends to undergo penance in order to appease Lord Shiva. While he is approaching to "Indrakeeladri", Arjuna is halted by a series of tests and enticed by several charms on his route. The structure of the performance is apparently developed through these tests and temptations. Reflecting on the structure of the performance, a Veedhi-natakamu performer says that Arjuna is enticed by Apsaras to distract from the penance, and these Apsaras are "Urvashi, Ramba, Menaka, and Thilottama", the scenes represents Arjuna's intention to undergo penance.

Arjuna arrives at the Indrakeeladri to undertake penance after these tests and temptations. Goddess Parvathi, who is watching Arjuna-tapassu, requests Lord Shiva to see the auspicious “fish-mark” on Arjuna’s back. Then both Shiva and Parvathi disguise themselves as hunters and descend to the earth. Shiva sends a demon named Muka in the form of a wild boar. The wild boar interrupts Arjuna-tapassu. Arjuna prepares to shoot the wild boar with his arrow. Lord Shiva also aims an arrow to the boar according to his plan. Lord Shiva and Arjuna releases their arrows at time to shoot the boar. Since he is disguised, Shiva is not recognised by Arjuna. They start fighting over who killed the boar. Arjuna releases many arrows on lord Shiva. After few minutes of fight, Arjuna observes that his quire is empty.

Now, Arjuna attempts to hit Shiva with Gandivam, and he is discouraged by Shiva grabbing the bow. As he loses his Gandivam, Arjuna begins to wrestle and fight with his fists. Again, Arjuna loses the fight against Shiva, and falls unconscious. Now, Lord Shiva shows to Parvathi the fish-mark on Arjuna’s back. After sometime, Arjunaarises back to consciousness. In the meantime, Shiva and Parvathi returns to their normal states from the disguise hunter. Looking at them, Arjuna realises that he has been fighting with lord Shiva, then he seeks for forgiveness from Shiva for his ignorance. Shiva is pleased by Arjuna’s bravery and devotion. Shiva finally grants Arjuna the deadly weapon, Pasupatastra.

2.2. Creating performance space for Arjuna-tapassu :

To perform Arjuna-tapassu in Dharmaraja festival, a huge wooden pole with small logs is

planted vertically in the temple courtyard. This pole is popularly known as Tapas-maanuin Telugu language. After it is erected, the height of the pole is approximately 30 meters. The entire pole is decorated with red and white horizontal stripes. To serve as steps, the pole is normally attached with approximately 30 tiny logs. A wooden plank, 1 meter length and 2 feet wide, is bolted on the top of the pole. This plant accommodates the enactment of Arjuna-tapassu on Indrakeeladri.

Around this pole, one-hectare land in the temple courtyard is used for both performers and devotees. The space between performers and devotees is not separated physically. The devotees occupy the space around the pole like a circular disc. Performance space is fixed inside this devotees’ space. The performance space is extended when it is needed during the performance. This extension of physical space happens when the performers comes closure to the devotees and they step back to offer space.

2.3. Processions to reach Indrakeeladri :

Arjuna-tapassuis performed twice in the festival. First one is performed on a folk theatre stage, and the second one is performed in the temple courtyards. There is a performance transformation from the stage-based performance to outdoor theatrical performance. This transformation happens with processions from the stage to the temple and from the temple to the pole. This transformation of the performance and physical space establishes indirect connection with fictional actions of Arjana reaching Indrakeeladri.

The outdoor performance of Arjuna-tapassuis performed by four actors of Veedhi-

natakamu. The performance is attended by five officiants. In this performance, Arjuna is represented by two people, a temple officiant and an actor. Here, the actors wear Veedhi-natakamu costumes, and the officiants wear saffron *dhoti*. First procession, from the stage to temple, is accompanied by music band with *pamba* and *dappu*. After reaching the temple, actors worship the Pandavas offering aburning camphor and breaking a coconut. Now, the officiants join with the actors to reach the pole. Again, the music band leads the procession from the temple to the pole. At the pole, officiants offer burning camphor and a coconut to the pole. Now, the actors commence the theatrical actions of Arjuna-tapassu. On the ground they perform the part with the combination of Arjuna, Shiva and Parvathi.

After the fight between Arjuna and Shiva, climbing the pole is commenced by the officiants and the actors. For this part, the actor and the officiant, who represent the Arjuna, reaches the logs of the pole to climb the pole. This action of climbing the pole is symbolic representation of the fictional action, Arjuna climbs the Indrakeeladri. This process of climbing appears as procession in vertical direction. The character, Arjuna, sings a song at each log to praise the Lord Shiva. After reaching top of the pole, the officiant, who represent Arjuna, sits on the wooden plank. At this point, the actor role is to deliver the dialogues and sing the songs, and the officiant's responsibility is to perform the rituals and penance to praise the lord Shiva. After finishing the penance, they throw the *prasadam* from the top of the pole to the devotees.

Thus, they complete the Arjuna-tapassu with actors and officiants. Here, processional enactments are not appeared, but the procession from the temple to the pole represents fictional space and action. Arjuna is represented by two actors in the performance of climbing the mountain. This performance also appears a procession in vertical direction.

It is observed that Arjuna-tapassu uses "multiple levels of performance space, horizontal to vertical" (Nagaraju 152). The part of the performance, fight between Shiva (disguised hunter) and Arjuna, is performed on the horizontal surface, on the temple courtyards. This horizontal space is intimate. The second part, climbing the mountain, is performed on the vertical pole. In this performance, devotees' view changes from horizontal to vertical. While the performers approaching the top of the pole, the intimacy between performers and devotees is reduced accordingly.

3. Driving the cattle and Uttara-gograhamamu(seizure of the cattle in the north) :

In Virata Parva, Padvas and Draupadi disguised in Virata's kingdom, and Uttara-gograhamamu is one of the episodes from the the Parva. In Dharmaraja festival, two folk theatre performances are organised, and they are Keechaka-vadha ("The slaying of Keechaka") and (Uttara-gograhamamu). These two performances are organised at various settings. While Keechaka-vadha is performed on Veedhi-natakamu stage, Uttara-gograhamamu is performed in outdoors and onstage. As it is sequel to Keechaka-vadha, Uttara-gograhamamu is performed after Keechaka-vadha. Outdoor performance of

Uttara-gograhanamu is one of the large-scale enactments in Dharmaraja festival. This performance is combination of processions, rituals and enactments.

3.1. Back ground story of Virata Parva :

Virata Parva starts after Pandavas spend “12 years of exile in the forest”. Pandavas choose to finish one-year exile incognito at Virat’s kingdom. Pandavas leave their armaments in a Jammi (Prosopis Cineraria) tree to hide their identity, and they reach Virata’s kingdom. As they invoke and request Kalika (Durga) to protect the armaments, Pandavas are promised by Kalika that only Arjuna can touch the armaments. After concealing the armaments, Pandavas and Draupadi reach Virata’s kingdom in their respective disguises: “Dharmaraju as Kankubhattu; Bhima as Valaludu; Arjuna as Brihannala (half male, half female); Nakula as Damagrandhi; Sahdeva as Tantripaludu’ and Draupadi as Malini”.

During Pandavas’ stay at Virata, Keechak, army commander of Virata, reaches the kingdom to visit his sister, Sudeshna, queen of the kingdom. Then he observes Malini (Draupadi in disguise), and falls in love with her beauty. As he could not control his lust, he tries to harass Draupadi sexually. Now, Draupadi complaints to Bhima, he suggests her to lure Keechaka late at night in the dancing room. Following Bhima’s plan, Draupadi invites Keechaka to the dancing room to yield to him there. When he reaches there, Keechaka finds Bhima instead of Draupadi. Then he is crushed to death in Bhima’s hands.

In the meantime, Duryodhana tries to expose Pandavas before their exile, so he can

send them back to the exile for 13 years. When he comes to know about the killing of Keechaka, Duryodhana deduces only Bhima could kill the Keechaka. Finally, Duryodhana finds the existence of Pandavas in Virata’s kingdom. Now, Duryodhana plans to provoke Pandavas into the war. For this, Duryodhana takes help from Susasana, king of Trigarta; he sends Susasana’s army to attack Virata’s kingdom from south taking help of Susasan, king of Trigarta. Another group of Duryodhana’s army astonishes in the north of Virata. Falling for Duryodhana’s trick, king Virata leads his army to defend Susasana’s army at the south. In the meantime, Duryodhana’s army rob the cattle at the north of Virata.

A messenger communicates to prince Uttara, son of Virata’s king, that Kauravas seized the herds. As the king of Virata is away to fight against Susasana, prince Uttara is requested to fight against Kauravas. When he is asked for the fight in front of the women, Uttara blushes with pride, and agrees to defend the Kauravas. Then, he goes for the fight taking Brihannala (Arjuna in disguise) as charioteer. Watching the Kauravas’ army in the battle field, Uttara is terrified, he jumps out of the chariot and tries to run away. Brihannala compels him by force to stay in the chariot. Brihannala drive the chariot to the Jammi tree in which Pandavas concealed the weapons. Here, after disclosing his identity, Arjuna points the direction where Pandavas concealed the armaments. However, Uttara cannot see the armaments other than snakes in the Jammi tree. After procuring the weapons, Arjuna asks Uttara to take the charge of charioteer. Prince Uttara

moves the chariot in front of the Kauravas' army. Arjuna fights with Kauravas, he kills Vikarma, wounds Karna, and lays them unconscious. Thus, Arjuna defeats the Kauravas and recovers the cattle of Virata.

3.2. Procession to Jammi Tree :

In this Parva, Veedhi-natakamu performers enact Keechaka-vadha, and the Uttara-gograhanamu on the stage, but they repeat few scenes to perform in outdoors, and these scenes are from Uttara goes for war to Arjuna recovers cattle. The performance of these scenes are associated with rituals, processions, and enactments. There are two processions are observed here. First procession is observed from the performance space of Veedhi-natakamu to temple hall. To complete this procession, actors and officiants takes *pradakshana* around the temple. After *pradakshana*, actors enter into the temple hall to seek blessings of Pandavas.

After seeking blessings, actors begin another procession from the temple to outdoor performance space, paddy field. Two actors, who play Brihannala and Uttara, settles in a bullock cart for this procession. Here, the bullock cart is symbolic representation of chariot driven by Brihannala in the story. During this procession, the two actors perform many comic actions such as Uttara runs away from the chariot, Brihannala chases him, Uttara hides in the crowd, Brihannala kicks him, Uttara cries for help, and Brihannala teases him for being coward. Usually devotees follow a procession, but they lead the procession here. Devotees walk in front of the cart, and offer space for the performers at various places on the way to paddy field. Along with the devotees, other

actors, in Veedhi-natakamu costumes, follow the procession. These actors represent Duryodhna, Dushasana, Karna and Bhishma. The procession ends once they reach the paddy field.

3.3. Performance Space to seize the cattle:

To perform Uttara-gograhanamu, performers select approximately four to six hectares of paddy field. The Jammi tree in the story is symbolically represented with a branch of real Jammi tree. This branch is erected at the centre of the selected space. Temple committee smooth the surface around this erected branch with radius of about six meters. This circular space is to perform rituals to commence the theatrical performance. Another space around this ritual space is to organise to drive the cattle. This space is starts approximately five meters radius from the erected branch, and ends approximately at 30 meters radius. After this range, devotees occupy the space to watch the performance.

3.4. Arjuna in action :

After the procession to the Jammi tree, the performers take *pradakshana* around it. Then, they tangle the props in the Jammi tree, and these props are a sceptre, a bow, few arrows, and a sword. They perform a ritual here putting sacred marks on the surface of the branch with vermilion and turmeric paste; offering coconut; performing *harathi*; and breaking a pumpkin.

Now, the performers begin the comical act that Uttara tires to fetch down the armaments from the Jammi tree. The enactment is centred around the Uttara, and the comic actions are follows: Uttara cannot see the weapons; he can see scorpions and snakes instead of the weapons; he demonstrates fear, and runs away

from the tree; as Arjuna motivates him, Uttara tries to approach the tree again and observes a decomposed dead body on the tree, he vomits, and faints; Uttara begs Arjuna to reach the palace; and After Arjuna brings the armaments, Uttara tries to lift it, but he cannot. During these comic actions, Uttara runs in the crowded devotees, Arjuna brings him back to the Jammi tree.

During the comic scenes of Uttara, performers who are in the costumes of Kauravas are with devotees, and they watch the performance until their part. These actors do not have many dialogues, actions and songs in the performance other than their physical presence in the performance. The fight between Arjuna and Kauravas are demonstrated with simple comic actions, and these actions are as follows: Duryodhana begs for life when Arjuna fights against him; Kauravas cries like babies when Arjuna assaults them; and Kauravas' moustache and head was shaved half (symbolically represents this action removing moustache and wigs of respective actors). Thus, performers demonstrate the actions how Kauravas lose the war against Arjuna.

Now, the actors, who play the characters Arjuna and Uttara, drive the cattle around the Jammi tree. After this symbolic representation, devotees drive the cattle around the tree. After three rounds around the tree, the cattle are driven away from the paddy field. It is the signal

that the performance of Uttara-gograhanamu is completed.

Conclusion :

This study was made to critically understand performance text, processional enactments and outdoor space in the outdoor theatre performances of Dharmaraja's festival in Chittoor district, Andhra Pradesh. when it was approached, the complexity of the study was to narrow the data. Since there were five outdoor theatre performances, it was not easy to ignore any one of the performances for this study. To overcome this challenge, the study selected three outdoor theatre performances that allows processional enactments. Thus, this study selected Bakasura-vadha, Arjuna-tapassu, and Uttara-gograhanamu to study performance text, processional enactments and outdoor space. All these performances were performed based on Mahabharatha text. In the processional enactments, the role of the text was very less other than improvising comic situations. There were many processions in the festival, and few of them were strongly associated with the enactments. These processional enactments initiated the devotees from the temple yards to outdoor performance spaces such as paddy fields and street corners. The outdoor performance space did not denote historical accuracy for any performance other than accommodating performances.

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